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Clinical Image

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Very rare Image for Rheumatoid tricuspid valve changes**Hadi abdulsalam Abo Aljadayel^{1*} and Prof Saied Saeid Hosseini²**¹Master Cardiac Surgery, Syrian and Arab Board in Cardiac Surgery²Heart valve Disease Research Centre, Rajaie Cardiovascular Medical and Research Center, Iran University of Medical Sciences***Corresponding Author:** Dr. Hadi abdulsalam Abo Aljadayel, Master, Syrian and Arab Board in Cardiac Surgery, Email: hadyaboaljadayel@yahoo.com***Received Date:*** Apr 29, 2020 / ***Accepted Date:*** May 08, 2020 / ***Published Date:*** May 11, 2020**Cite this article as:** Hadi abdulsalam Abo Aljadayel, Saied Saeid Hosseini. 2020. Very rare Image for Rheumatoid tricuspid valve changes. J Cardiovasc Surg Heart Dis. 2: 12-13.**Copyright:** This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited. Copyright © 2020; Hadi abdulsalam Abo Aljadaye**Keywords:** Valvular disease; Rheumatismal changes; Tricuspid valve disease**Introduction**

Rheumatic tricuspid valve disease occurs in association with rheumatic involvement of the mitral aortic valves combined. The third world still have a significant prevalence of rheumatic tricuspid valvular disease. The preponderance of cases is in young women. Rheumatic tricuspid disease usually results in a regurgitant valve with variable amounts of stenosis, Borders of the stenotic tricuspid orifice are usually fibrous and thickened, although peripheral portions of the leaflets remain thin. The hallmark of organic tricuspid stenosis is commissural fusion. All commissures are usually equally fused, but occasionally fusion is limited to the anteroseptal commissure. Chordal thickening and fusion are usually mild, and calcification is usually absent.

Case of 30 years old lady who underwent cardiac surgery for mitral, Aortic, tricuspid valve replacement.

Disclosures:

The authors have no conflicts of interest to disclose.

We took this Image for the Tricuspid valve intra operatively figure 1,2.

Figure 1

Figure 2

